

STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT ISSUES IN UZBEKISTAN PSYCHOLOGY

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In recent years, a number of fundamental reforms have been implemented in the field of educational institution management in our republic, and the necessary legal and regulatory frameworks have been created. Ensuring the effectiveness of the fundamental changes and reforms being implemented to build a new Uzbekistan and the foundation of the Third Renaissance depends on the introduction of effective mechanisms for managing the public education system. Today, progress requires a modern leader to keep pace with the times, not be afraid of innovations, quickly accept news and information, process and use it in their place, strive to create new ideas and turn them into tangible products, and implement foreign best practices and innovative technologies in their pedagogical team. It is advisable for the head of an educational institution to demonstrate a thirst for new and modern, worldly knowledge and ideas, to try to creatively approach life problems, to develop specific projects, to test innovations and summarize their effectiveness, and to strive to continuously improve the skills of himself and his subordinates. The fulfillment of these tasks requires professionalism, high-level knowledge of his field, initiative, resourcefulness, inquisitiveness, a desire for innovation, and organizational skills from each head of an educational institution.

In his reports at a joint session of the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, emphasized the importance of transitioning to a modern management system for the effective organization of the activities of heads of sectors and regions, and set important tasks for representatives of the industry and scientists of our republic. That is why today the issues of management and leadership psychology remain one of the areas that are being effectively studied by Uzbek scientists, especially in the psychological direction. We can clearly see this in the scientific research carried out by B.A.Abdullayev, Sh.Kh.Abdullaeva, D.S.Abdullajanova, K.S.Aliyeva, N.Boimurodov, E.S.Yoziev, X.A.Kadirova, N.T.Kariyeva, V.M.Karimova, I.I.Makhmudov, A.M.Makhmudov, D.G.Mukhamedova, A.S.Nazarov, N.A.Ruzikulov, E.N.Sattarov, O.R.Shamiyeva, A.M.Shonazarov, O.E.Hayitov, E.G.Goziev and others. We found it necessary to

dwell in more detail on a number of scientific research works carried out by leading psychological scientists below.

D.G.Mukhamedova's doctoral dissertation entitled "Improving socio-psychological technologies for training educational managers for innovative activities" studies the socio-psychological aspects of the process of training educational managers for innovative activities in higher educational institutions. This work is notable for the fact that it clarifies the factors that negatively affect the innovative activities of educational managers, the criteria for evaluating this activity, and reveals the methodological and methodological aspects of training educational managers for innovative activities. In his research, the author describes the basics of the educational manager training program for innovative activities of higher education institutions and highlights the following principles: 1) the principle of humanism; 2) the principle of democratization; 3) the principle of scientificity; 4) the principle of coherence, continuity and integration; 5) the principle of individualization; 6) the principle of improving and directing the training of educational managers for innovative activities; 7) the principle of innovation; 8) the principle of interactivity; 9) the principle of varying the content and form of training [3; 20].

The dissertation by D.S. Abdullajanova on the topic "Socio-psychological characteristics of women's activity in management" is devoted to the scientific substantiation of the practical importance of forming a personnel reserve in the selection and appointment of women to management positions, increasing the efficiency of their use in the service, and it identifies the socio-psychological characteristics of women's activity in management. The study examined the relationship between motivation to achieve success and specialization in women's activity in management, the different effects of different levels of motivation and motivation to avoid failure on activity, the impact of leadership types on risk-taking in women, and the manifestation of a number of psychological aspects. It is noteworthy that the dissertation work developed a training program aimed at increasing women's activity in management, forming a female personnel reserve, and developing communication skills [1; 48].

N.A. Ruzikulov's scientific research is devoted to the issues of psychological support for improving the management activities of the head of a general educational institution, in this work the specific difficulties of the management process, the importance of psychological factors in increasing the efficiency of management activities are revealed. The author found that the heads of educational institutions are sufficiently self-confident, sociable, independent,

they feel themselves as individuals. This category of leaders assess self-development as a leading factor in their professional activities. It was found that in the professional and personal development of the head of an educational institution, his professional activities and the formation of his personality determine each other [4; 18].

The Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in psychology by A.M. Makhmudov on the topic "Socio-psychological characteristics of the formation of management skills in young leaders" is dedicated to the development of effective mechanisms for identifying the specific features of the development and formation of management skills in young leaders engaged in management activities in various fields. The study analyzed the factors influencing the formation and development of management skills in young leaders. It is worth noting that a new approach to determining and studying the level of development of management skills, according to which self-awareness of young leaders is a leading stimulus for their further development, has been introduced into the practice of psychological research on the study of leadership in the republic. The fact that this study was conducted with the recognition of the leadership competence in managerial activities and the identification of the levels of expression of these competencies in young managers increases the possibilities of applying this research work to the field of personnel resource formation [2; 140].

The doctoral dissertation by O.E. Khayitov on the topic "Modeling the psychological competence of middle-level managers of higher education institutions" is devoted to the study of the system of individual-psychological, age-, gender-, and profession-related socio-psychological qualities of the formation of competencies in the process of modeling the psychological competence of middle-level managers of higher education institutions. The research work focuses on issues of competence and competence, based on the analysis of various approaches, indicates levels of competence, and concludes that the components that make up competence (knowledge set, skills, communication standards) are the basis for the development of managerial, personal and functional competencies in a leader. The dissertation empirically studies the possibilities of modeling the psychological competence of a manager. In the comprehensive model of developing psychological competence in a middle manager, given by the author, 38 competencies are identified as priority competencies [6; 250].

In the research of A.M. Shonazarov, it was found that "among the

components of socio-psychological competence that are taken into account when appointing school principals, the cognitive and social components have a predominant character, the socio-psychological competence of a leader is most often manifested in the ability to influence a person in interpersonal relationships, and most of the factors that prevent the manifestation of the level of socio-psychological competence of leaders are explained by external influences. The scientific conclusion is that in developing the socio-psychological competence of leaders working in the education system, a comprehensive and continuous approach based on psychotechnologies to the development of its affective, reflexive, and socio-cognitive components is effective” [5; 152].

Thus, the scientific research work carried out by our country's scientists has shown that there are manifestations of a comprehensive approach to the problem of management, that is, it has become clear that the scientific research carried out can be generalized in a holistic manner in specific areas. It is important that in their scientific research, issues of educational management, including the training of highly qualified managerial personnel for the continuous education system, the development of their professional competencies, the optimization of the management system of educational institutions, the preparation of future managers for professional management activities, their selection and selection, were deeply studied as the object of research work.

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